

Evaluation of Filling Materials for Breast Phantoms Using Texture Analysis

Júlia Miranda Brito
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0004-0783-8380

Lúisa Tonin Arruda
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0009-1953-4540

Maria Clara Mendes dos Santos
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-4208-2804

Pedro Faria de Bessa
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-6412-4668

Pedro Cunha Carneiro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-0120-5273

Ana Claudia Patrocínio
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-9376-7689

Abstract— In this study, beeswax and paraffin were tested to represent the texture of mammographic phantoms. The aim is to identify the most appropriate filling material for developing a breast phantom by analyzing texture attributes using digital mammographic images. The methodology was divided in four main stages, starting with the development of the phantom, which involved developing experimental structures using a 3D printing with polylactic acid (PLA) as the base material. The structures were intended to be filled with beeswax and paraffin for texture analysis. The next step was the image acquisition, which was acquired using a clinical mammography system under standard conditions and eight regions of interest (ROIs) were manually segmented. In the third stage, radiomic texture features were extracted from the segmented ROIs using Haralick descriptors, skewness and kurtosis, calculated through Gray-Level Co-Occurrence matrix (GLCM) in MATLAB. Finally, the fourth stage involved statistical analysis, in which Gaussian curves were used to evaluate feature robustness across materials, and bar charts were applied to assess each attribute's ability to distinguish between different internal regions of the phantom. It was concluded that the paraffin is the most indicated material, mainly due to its ability to simulate anatomical and pathological variability. This characteristic makes it more aligned with the objective of creating a configurable and accessible imaging simulator for clinical and research applications.

Keywords — *mammography, phantom, texture analysis, radiomics*

I. INTRODUCTION

Phantoms are simulator objects that replicate the radiographic characteristics of biological tissues, allowing imaging studies without exposing patients to radiation. They are used for calibrating image acquisition equipment, in quality control and providing professional training in the interpretation of clinical exams [1].

One of the most critical limitations of mammographic phantoms is the inadequate simulation of the visual texture of breast tissue. Texture plays an essential role in the detection of subtle abnormalities, such as microcalcification, architectural distortions and spiculated

masses [2]. Previous studies evaluating the morphological realism of anthropomorphic breast phantoms using radiomic features have found notable discrepancies when compared to real clinical images [3]. The inconsistency between phantom textures and real images reinforces the need for complementary strategies capable of assessing image realism more precisely.

The last decade has seen advances in processing and analysis lead to medical images being treated as sources of measurable data that reflect the physiology [4]. Various image descriptors can be obtained from medical imaging through radiomic techniques, exceeding the subjectivity of traditional visual examination [5]. Radiomics is not an automatization of diagnosis, rather, it is a complementary tool and the radiologist's analysis is still considered the gold standard [5, 6].

This approach has been widely used in oncology, resulting in more accurate diagnoses, and avoiding unnecessary biopsies or therapies. In the context of breast cancer, radiomics has shown promising results in characterizing tumor heterogeneity and distinguishing malignant from benign lesions, improving diagnostic performance [7]. Another important application lies in creating radiomics models to predict or prognosticate clinical outcomes, which relies on the reproducibility of extracted features, that is, characteristics that remain trustworthy and consistent across different settings [8].

Radiomics is a systematic process that starts with image acquisition and segmentation of regions of interest (ROIs). From these ROIs, quantitative features are extracted to describe the tissue characteristics [4, 9]. Among these, second-order statistics are important for measuring image texture because they capture spatial interactions between pixels and indicate image heterogeneity [4]. Texture, in this context, relates to gray-level variation patterns and is essential for identifying tissue structures. After that, these characteristics can be examined using statistical techniques to facilitate comparisons and finding models [4, 9].

The purpose of this paper was to identify whether there are significant differences between filler materials of a breast simulator prototype by analyzing texture attributes extracted from a digital mammographic image. The analysis is based

on radiomic features such. as Haralick descriptors, skewness and kurtosis, to determine which material best replicates the visual texture characteristics relevant for realistic phantom design.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Phantom

For this paper, a set of experimental structures was developed to evaluate the textural behavior of selected materials, serving as a preliminary step toward the development of a complete phantom. These structures were computationally modeled and produced by additive manufacturing (3D printing) using Polylactic Acid (PLA). The material was chosen based on their compatibility with radiation interaction, ease of replication, and cost-effectiveness [10].

The phantom under development is intended to be a low-cost, anthropomorphic, and highly configurable model for mammographic applications. Its design aims to allow the modular inclusion of regions of interest that simulate common breast pathologies and anatomical variations, as well as elements specifically intended for quantitative assessments of image quality.

B. Image acquisition

The structure's digital mammography image was acquired using a Mammomat SIEMENS clinical mammography system (tungsten anode) The technique parameters were 33 kVp, 40 mAs and the acquisition performed in automatic exposure mode. The phantom was positioned under compression, and the image was acquired in the cranial-caudal (CC) view, as shown in Figure 1. An image was saved in DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) format.

Fig. 1. Digital mammographic image of the prototype. The letter P refer to the prototype's 3D printing material (PLA), while the letters C and G refer to the filler materials beeswax (C) and paraffin gel (G)

Each visible square in the image was segmented into a

region of interest (ROI) to enable localized texture analysis. Although the phantom contained 16 squares, only those with structures printed in PLA (marked with the letter P in Figure 1) were selected to study. This was done to focus specifically on the analysis of beeswax and gel paraffin as filling materials. In total, eight ROIs were manually segmented using the ImageJ software.

C. Texture features

The distribution of gray-level values among pixels in a ROI determines texture in digital images, and it can be visualized as a three-dimensional map of pixel intensities [11]. This distribution creates tonal variation patterns that help to perceive surfaces and depth, and also express important information about their relationship with the surrounding environment [12].

To quantify the texture, Haralick descriptors were used. These descriptors are based on statistical analysis of the spatial relationships between gray levels in an image, represented by the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). The GLCM quantifies the frequency of pairs of pixel intensities occurring at specific distances and orientations, allowing for the extraction of various statistical measures [12]. These following 14 Haralick features were used, which describe different aspects of grayscale's spatial organization:

1. Angular Second Moment: this feature measures the homogeneity of the texture, which is high for homogeneous images.
2. Contrast: this feature estimates the local intensity variation by calculating the difference between the grey levels of adjacent pixels in the image, being lower for smaller measures.
3. Correlation: this measures the linearity between the gray levels of neighboring pixels, revealing hidden patterns or smooth areas.
4. Variance: this feature measures the intensity change in the background of the image.
5. Inverse Difference Moment: this measures the local homogeneity, highlighting subtle changes.
6. Sum Average: this calculates the average of the background tones.
7. Sum Variance: this indicates the variability of background tones.
8. Sum Entropy: this indicates the amount of information between two neighboring pixels.
9. Entropy: this quantifies the information resulting from the relationships between pixels.
10. Difference Variance: this calculates the variability with the mean centered at zero.
11. Difference Entropy: this measures the disorder between the background pixels.

12. Information Measure of Correlation 1 (IMC1): this quantifies the correlation by analyzing the entropy of individual elements and their paired combinations.
13. Information Measure of Correlation 2 (IMC2): this also measures correlation but based on the similarity between the entropies.
14. Maximal Correlation Coefficient (MCC): this indicates the heterogeneity in the gray-level distribution.

In addition to these, skewness was used to measure the asymmetry of the gray-level distribution around the mean, indicating whether there are more dark or bright pixels in the image. Kurtosis was also used to quantify the occurrence of intense peaks and long tails in the gray-level distribution [13].

The attributes were extracted using a MATLAB script. The GLCM was computed considering a pixel distance of 1 and four orientations (0° , 45° , 90° , and 135°). Each attribute's final value was obtained by averaging results from all orientations.

D. Statistical analysis

Two distinct selection criteria were used to evaluate the performance of texture attributes. First, the Gaussian curve was used to evaluate the stability of attributes across both filling material, beeswax and paraffin. This technique consists of developing a normal distribution based on mean and standard deviation normalized values. Attributes whose curves overlap most can be interpreted as indicating little difference between the filler materials. In other words, both beeswax and gel paraffin do not alter this texture descriptor. Thus, this descriptor can be interpreted as invariant to the material used.

The second method used a bar graph, where each bar corresponds to the attribute value of the ROI for each material: ROI for beeswax filling and ROI for gel paraffin filling (Fig. 1). Thus, graphs were generated for each attribute, and each bar represented the four ROIs. These graphs allowed for the analysis of the structural heterogeneity of the materials.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The initial analysis focused on evaluating the establishment of texture features attributes in relation to the material for filling used in the structures. For this, sixteen gaussian curves were created to represent the normal distributions for beeswax and paraffin. A high degree of overlap suggests that the attributes are not sensitive to differences in filler materials (beeswax and gel paraffin), indicating greater stability and reliability when used to evaluate structures in phantoms, regardless of the specific composition. Furthermore, it can be inferred that both materials produce images with similar texture.

After examining all the gaussians, the four attributes that showed the highest overlap were variance, sum average, sum variance and entropy, as shown in Figure 2. This selection considered the nearest averages of similar materials and standard deviation also.

Fig. 2. Results of the Haralick four-descriptor Gaussian analysis method. For these curves, a single image with the four ROIs filled with beeswax and another image with the four ROIs filled with paraffin gel were considered

In this context, the variance indicates that beeswax and paraffin produce similar intensity variations, sum average shows that the overall brightness remains consistent between materials and sum variance suggests a uniform response to tonal variation. These three Haralick texture descriptors are related to background implying a minimal influence of materials on background tonal behavior. And entropy, by quantifying the amount of information in pixel relationships, revealed that both fillings generate comparable levels of complexity in texture organization.

These findings indicate that these four texture features are less sensitive to the type of filling material used. Therefore, to achieve consistent texture representation regardless of material, both beeswax and paraffin may be considered equivalent in these aspects.

The next step was to assess the ability of each texture attribute to distinguish between different regions of the phantom. For this purpose, bar charts were generated for each material separately, allowing the comparison of feature values across the four selected ROIs.

The goal was to identify attributes capable of capturing structural heterogeneity within the same material, then the more variable the size of the bars the better is the effect. In Figure 3, there are the fourth results of this method, which are: angular second moment, contrast and skewness.

In terms of angular second moment, gel paraffin showed greater sensitivity, especially in ROI 2. For contrast, gel paraffin also presented results more favored, with broader variation among ROIs, particularly between ROI 2 and ROI 3 whereas beeswax showed similar values in these regions, indicating lower regional distinction. Regarding skewness, both materials showed higher values in ROI 2 compared to the other regions. However, gel paraffin exhibited a much more pronounced peak, suggesting a possible hypersensitivity to this material. In contrast, beeswax presented a more subtle difference, with ROI 2 displaying approximately twice the skewness of the other ROIs.

These results suggest that gel paraffin provides greater differentiation among internal regions, which is desirable in a phantom designed to simulate heterogeneous tissue

structures. However, beeswax offered more stable responses in certain attributes, which could be advantageous depending on the application.

Fig. 3. Results of bar chart analyze method.

IV. CONCLUSION

Considering the goal of developing a low-cost, anthropomorphic, and modular phantom for mammographic applications, the results indicate that both beeswax and paraffin are viable as filling materials. However, paraffin showed greater distinction between internal regions while maintaining consistent texture behavior, which is essential for quantitative assessments of image quality. Its performance aligns with the phantom's design intent of supporting anatomical variability and simulating pathological features, reinforcing its suitability for continued use in the construction of an accessible and configurable imaging simulator.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the *Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG)*, *Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES)*, *Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq)* and the *Grupo de Imagens Médicas* for the financial and technological support provided for the development of this study and work.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Sousa, B. Matheus, and H. Schiabel, "Development of a structured breast phantom for evaluating cade/dx schemes applied on 2d mammography," *Biomedical Physics & Engineering Express*, vol. 4, no. 4, p. 045018, 2018.
- [2] R. J. Acciavatti, E. A. Cohen, O. H. Maghsoudi, A. Gastouniotti, L. Pantalone, M.-K. Hsieh, B. Barufaldi, P. R. Bakic, J. Chen, E. F. Conant, *et al.*, "Calculation of radiomic features to validate the textural realism of physical anthropomorphic phantoms for digital mammography," in *15th International Workshop on Breast Imaging (IWBI2020)*, vol. 11513, pp. 65–71, SPIE, 2020.
- [3] A. Cuccaro, A. Dell'Aversano, G. Ruvio, J. Browne, and R. Solimene, "Incoherent radar imaging for breast cancer detection and experimental validation against 3d multimodal breast phantoms," *Journal of Imaging*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 23, 2021.
- [4] R. J. Gillies, P. E. Kinahan, and H. Hricak, "Radiomics: images are more than pictures, they are data," *Radiology*, vol. 278, no. 2, pp. 563–577, 2016.
- [5] J. E. Van Timmeren, D. Cester, S. Tanadini-Lang, H. Alkadhi, and B. Baessler, "Radiomics in medical imaging—"how-to" guide and critical reflection," *Insights into imaging*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 91, 2020.
- [6] M. Elmahdy and R. Sebro, "Radiomics analysis in medical imaging research," *Journal of medical radiation sciences*, vol. 70, no. 1, p. 3, 2023.
- [7] Z. Li, L. Yu, X. Wang, H. Yu, Y. Gao, Y. Ren, G. Wang, and X. Zhou, "Diagnostic performance of mammographic texture analysis in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant breast tumors," *Clinical Breast Cancer*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. e621–e627, 2018.
- [8] Y. Balagurunathan, Y. Gu, H. Wang, V. Kumar, O. Grove, S. Hawkins, J. Kim, D. B. Goldgof, L. O. Hall, R. A. Gatenby, *et al.*, "Reproducibility and prognosis of quantitative features extracted from ct images," *Translational oncology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 72–87, 2014.
- [9] B. A. Varghese, S. Y. Cen, D. H. Hwang, and V. A. Duddalwar, "Texture analysis of imaging: what radiologists need to know," *American Journal of Roentgenology*, vol. 212, no. 3, pp. 520–528, 2019.
- [10] M. S. D. Pinheiro *et al.*, "Análise de materiais e desenvolvimento de objeto simulador mamográfico," 2024.
- [11] G. Castellano, L. Bonilha, L. Li, and F. Cendes, "Texture analysis of medical images," *Clinical radiology*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 1061–1069, 2004.
- [12] R. M. Haralick, K. Shanmugam, and I. H. Dinstein, "Textural features for image classification," *IEEE Transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics*, no. 6, pp. 610–621, 2007.

- [13] F. J. Cardoso, A. C. Patrocínio, M. C. M. Santos, J. M. Brito, and H. Schiabel, “Analytical software for visual and quantitative comparison of real mammography and phantom breast cancer imaging,” *Academia Oncology*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2025.